

WAYS OF INCREASE EFFICIENCY IN BUILDING MATERIALS ENTERPRISES

Akhmadalieva Mokhigul Kadirovna

Fergana State University part-time
department social humanitarian
teacher of the science department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7956433>

Abstract:

With the transition to the market economy, the meaning of the interpretation and hierarchy of efficiency criteria has changed, since the main goal of business activity in the conditions of market relations is profit, the criteria of economic efficiency are the maximization of profit per unit of capital expenditure (resources) with a high level of labor quality and the problems facing the industry in ensuring the competitiveness of products. illuminated.

Basic concepts: efficiency, operational efficiency, financial efficiency, building materials, technological process.

Enter

In recent years, the construction materials industry has been growing significantly. As a result of the rapid influx of foreign investments into the construction industry of our country, the production of sustainable and environmentally friendly raw materials and products is being launched. In the decree of the President of June 9, 2021 "On additional measures to increase the industrial potential of the regions", all the organizational and practical mechanisms of raising the construction materials production sector to a new level were determined. Systemic reforms such as increasing production efficiency in construction enterprises, modernization of branch enterprises, technical and technological upgrading, introduction of advanced technologies in the deep processing of local raw materials contribute to the development of export-import practices in the construction materials industry.

Increasing economic efficiency is a complex process that requires a comprehensive approach, taking into account the financial, operational and production aspects of the enterprise. Economic efficiency is measured by the ratio of production costs to product value. The goal of increasing economic efficiency is to reduce costs while maintaining or increasing product value. The production process in an enterprise is complex and requires increased control and high coordination.

The main part

Achieving economic efficiency requires an understanding of the production process and the interaction of various elements. It is important to identify areas of production where costs can be reduced without compromising production quality. This can be done through a combination of process optimization, automation and improved resource utilization. Financial efficiency is also important for enterprises producing building materials. It is necessary to ensure that the company operates within its budget and has sufficient funds to cover its

operating costs. Financial efficiency can be achieved by reducing costs, increasing revenues and improving the efficiency of the financial management system.

As a result of the enterprise's activity, the volume of product production (sales) or financial result is expressed in the indicators of production efficiency and financial efficiency. With the transition to the market economy, the meaning of the interpretation and hierarchy of efficiency criteria has changed, since the main goal of business activity in the conditions of market relations is profit, the economic efficiency criteria consists of maximizing profit per unit of capital expenditure (resources) with a high level of quality of work and ensuring the competitiveness of products. Operational efficiency is a key factor in the success of construction materials manufacturing enterprises. It involves optimizing the process and using resources to ensure that the company produces the desired product at the lowest possible cost. It is possible to increase operational efficiency by reducing the number of stages in the production process, increasing the speed of production and minimizing the amount of waste generated in the production process. The most important tasks of the building materials production industry are: wide use of local raw materials, development of product production, improvement of their quality and construction is to reduce the cost. Efficiency is evaluated in terms of achieving economic goals. They can be long-term, for example, continuous growth and development, or short-term, for example, to ensure the stabilization of the economy in response to unpredictable events, called economic turbulence. Every enterprise is evaluated by economic indicators based on the effectiveness of its activities at a high level. (Picture 1) operational efficiency can be increased by increasing production speed and minimizing the amount of waste generated in the production process. The most important tasks of the construction materials production industry are: wide use of local raw materials, development of product production, improvement of their quality, and reduction of construction costs. Efficiency is evaluated in terms of achieving economic goals. They can be long-term, for example, continuous growth and development, or short-term, for example, to ensure the stabilization of the economy in response to unpredictable events, called economic turbulence. Every enterprise is evaluated by economic indicators based on the effectiveness of its activities at a high level. (Picture 1) operational efficiency can be increased by increasing production speed and minimizing the amount of waste generated in the production process. The most important tasks of the construction materials production industry are: wide use of local raw materials, development of product production, improvement of their quality, and reduction of construction costs. Efficiency is evaluated in terms of achieving economic goals. They can be long-term, for example, continuous growth and development, or short-term, for example, to ensure the stabilization of the economy in response to unpredictable events, called economic turbulence. Every enterprise is evaluated by economic indicators based on the effectiveness of its activities at a high level. (Picture 1) is to increase their quality and reduce the cost of construction. Efficiency is evaluated in terms of achieving economic goals. They can be long-term, for example, continuous growth and development, or short-term, for example, to ensure the stabilization of the economy in response to unpredictable events, called economic turbulence. Every enterprise is evaluated by economic indicators based on the effectiveness of its activities at a high level. (Picture 1) is to increase their quality and reduce the cost of construction. Efficiency is evaluated in terms of achieving economic goals. They can be long-term, for example, continuous growth and development, or short-term, for example, to ensure the stabilization of the economy in response to unpredictable events,

called economic turbulence. Every enterprise is evaluated by economic indicators based on the effectiveness of its activities at a high level. (Picture 1) Every enterprise is highly evaluated by economic indicators based on the efficiency of its activity. (Picture 1) Every enterprise is highly evaluated by economic indicators based on the efficiency of its activity. (Picture 1)

Figure 1. Main economic indicators

The composition of the main economic indicators may change for each enterprise, more precisely, for each field of activity. Increasing economic efficiency in enterprises producing building materials requires a comprehensive approach, taking into account all aspects of business. It is important to identify areas of production where costs can be reduced without compromising the quality of the product being produced, and to ensure that the enterprise operates within its budget and has sufficient funds to cover its operational costs. In addition, operational efficiency must be optimized to ensure that the company produces the desired product at the lowest possible cost.

In recent years, we can observe the increase in the number of several construction materials production enterprises in the Fergana region of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2021 in Table 1 below. With the high indicators in this table, it means that not only the number of enterprises has increased, that is, the volume of manufactured products has increased during the four years. However, in the following table construction materials number of manufacturing enterprises Compared to 2018, we can see an increase of 29 by 2021 and the volume of products produced.

		in 2018		in 2019		in 2020		in 2021	
o	Type of activity of enterprises producing construction materials	comp any number	I/ch product quantity Tn	ompan y number	I/ch product size tn	ompa ny number	I/ch product size tn	om pan y nu mber	I/ch product size tn
	Granules, crushed stone powder and other types of stone crushing	6	61 620.0	8	227256.0	9	182 433.0	0	185249.2
	Portland cement	3	1166818.5	5	1227500.6	10	1758854.6	3	1576226.3
	cement, products other than concrete or artificial stone.	7	5 573.9	9	6 531.2	17	16 116.1	2	33275.7
	Total	16		22		36		5	

**Building materials dynamics of manufacturing enterprises
Table 2.**

In this direction, important initiatives and reforms are being implemented in order to achieve new resources. The essence of the problem of increasing economic efficiency in production is to increase the unit of costs for each of the economic results in the process of using existing resources. . The most important factor for increasing efficiency is scientific and technological progress. Automation of production, wide introduction of advanced

technologies, creation and use of new materials helps to reduce labor and material costs, as well as to increase the number of manufactured products.

Conclusions and suggestions

Production efficiency is directly related to the saving procedure. In order to meet the growing needs of fuel energy raw materials and materials, saving resources should become a decisive source. Industry plays an important role in addressing these issues:

- It is the use of machines, equipment, raw materials, fuel and energy resources that ensure high efficiency in creating and equipping the national economy, as well as technological processes of high-efficiency low-waste and zero-waste products.

- Today, our country consumes much more fuel, energy and metal compared to developed countries. This leads to a lack of resources in large-scale production, which forces us to increase all new funds for the expansion of the raw material and fuel-energy base. Increase largely depends on effective use of basic resources.

- Intensive use of the created production potential, achieving the production rhythm and maximum loading of the equipment is to increase the complexity of its work. Important organizational and economic factors play a role in increasing production efficiency. First of all, it is one of the forms of organization in development and production: concentration, specialization, cooperation,

is to improve combinations

Improved management forms, methods of planning, economic incentives to increase efficiency affect the entire economic mechanism.

References:

- 1.Рахимова, Қ. Н. Қ. (2022). Яшил бизнес аҳамиятининг ортиб боришининг ижтимоий-иқтисодий зарурати. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 880-885.
- 2.Rakhimova, K. (2022). SOCIO-ECONOMIC NECESSITY OF INCREASING THE IMPORTANCE OF GREEN BUSINESS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(4), 1034-1037.
- 3.Husanbek, Q., & Raximova, K. N. (2022). OILAVIY KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI VA ZARURIYATI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 24, 1103-1108.
- 4.Мохигул, А., & Рахимова, К. (2022). ҚУРИЛИШ МАТЕРИЛЛАРИ САНОВАТИ КОРХОНАЛАРИДА ИШЛАБ ЧИҚИШ ПОТЕНЦИАЛИДАН САМАРАЛИ ФОЙДАЛАНИШ СТРАТЕГИЯСИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 24, 999-1002.
- 5.Raximova, K. N., & Abdurahmon Mominjon og, A. (2022). YASHIL HOM-ASHYOLARDAN QURILISH SOHALARIDA FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 24, 957-960.
- 6.Qizi, R. K. N. M., & Kadirovna, A. M. (2022). ISHCHI KUCHIGA TALAB VA TAKLIFNI ISTIQBOLLASHTIRISH. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 8, 149-153.
- 7.Рахимова, К. Н., Турсунов, О., Мирзаев, Р. Б., Ахмадалиева, М. К., & Кодиров, А. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА «ЯШИЛ МОЛИЯ» ТИЗИМИНИ ЙЎЛГА ҚЎЙИШ ВА ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 28, 90-96.

- 8.Kizlarkhon, R. (2022). ECONOMICAL USE OF LAND AND WATER RESOURCES WITH THE OPTIONS. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(09), 148-151.
- 9.Абдусаматов, Д. А. (2022). КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ПРИЕМНИКОВ ОПТИЧЕСКОГО ИЗЛУЧЕНИЯ ДЛЯ РАЗРАБОТКИ ОПТОЭЛЕКТРОННЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-ИЗМЕРИТЕЛЬНЫХ СИСТЕМ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 24, 986-988.
- 10.Абдусаматов, Д. А., & Рахимов, Н. Р. (2021). Технологические Особенности Изготовления Афн-Пленок И Приборных Структур На Их Основе.
- 11.Рахимов, Н. Р., & Абдусаматов, Д. А. (2021). Определение Природы Возникновения Аномального Фотонапряжения И Разработка Оптрона На Их Основе.
- 12.Madvaliyev B., Rakhimova K. The Role of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship in the Economy //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 264-267.
- 13.Абдусаматов, Д. А. (2022). Классификация Приемников Оптического Излучения Для Разработки Оптоэлектронных Информационно-Измерительных Систем. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 24, 986-988.
- 14.Kuldashov, O. H., Komilov, A. O., & Abdusamatov, D. A. (2022). COMPUTER MODEL OF IONIZER. *International Journal of Advance Scientific Research*, 2(12), 133-139.
15. Consumer.gov.uz - Raqobatni rivojlantirish va iste'molchilar huquqlarini himoya qilish qo'mitasi. 23/05/2022
16. utg.uz – “O‘ztransgaz” АК. 27.01.2022
- 17.Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo‘jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti. Kitoblar.
- 18.Kadirovna, A. M. (2022). CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES OF THE LEVEL OF USE OF PRODUCTION POTENTIAL. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(10), 137-141.
- 19.Akhmadaliyeva, M. (2022). REFORMS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN OUR COUNTRY. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 22, 439-442.
- 20.Мохигул, А., & Рахимова, К. (2022). Курилиш материаллари саноати корхоналарида ишлаб чиқиш потенциалидан самарали фойдаланиш стратегиясини шакллантириш йўналишлари. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 24, 999-1002.
- 21.Burkxonovich, M. R., & Kadirovna, A. M. (2022). IMPROVEMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL ECONOMIC IMPACT OF PRODUCT COST REDUCTION ON THE BASIS OF COST-EFFECTIVE USE OF RESOURCES. *Thematics Journal of Economics*, 8(1).
- 22.Рахимова, К. Н., Турсунов, О., Мирзаев, Р. Б., Ахмадалиева, М. К., & Кодиров, А. (2022). Ўзбекистонда «Яшил Молия» Тизимини Йўлга Қўйиш Ва Такмиллаштириш Йўналишлари. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 28, 90-96.
- 23.Qizi, R. K. N. M., & Kadirovna, A. M. (2022). Ishchi Kuchiga Talab Va Taklifni Istiqbollashtirish. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 8, 149-153.